

**Motivation in Learning Danish Language: a case
Study on expatriates in Denmark**

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1. Introduction

Motivation considered a central element influencing foreign language acquisition. Therefore, researchers have been studying it for decades, and because it is impossible to define motivation easily, they have arrived at numerous different definitions (Gardner, 2005). For example, Kleinginna & Kleinginna (1981) refer to this concept with 102 statements, because of the concept complexity and Keller (1983) states, “motivation refers to the choices people make as to what experiences or goals they will approach or avoid, and the degree of effort they will exert in this respect” (p. 389). Motivation has various features; it demonstrates numerous aspects in motivated individuals. For example, they maybe aim-oriented, manifest effort, accomplish the goal, show resilience, attend to necessary assignments to accomplish the purposes, and many other features.

Motivation has been studied in many fields, and second language acquisition has been one of them. Motivation within L2 has gone through different stages. Researchers have formulated different theories to discover the critical features of motivation in L2, how to measure it, how to motivate students, from Gardner’s theory with his socio-educational model (Gardner 1985, 2001, 2005) to the L2 Motivational Self System (Dörnyei 2005, see also Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2009 & 2011) and to self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985, 2000 & 2017). Hence, the importance of motivation in learning a foreign language comes into question. There are many advantages of learning foreign languages, such as advancing in a career, better cognitive functions, gaining confidence, and many others, yet it is not necessary to learn a foreign language. For that reason, motivation is a significant factor in learning an L2/FL (Gardner, 2007).

The field of motivation in second language acquisition/Foreign language has been thrived with countless studies and research, particularly with English, given it is an international,

scientific, and technological language. However, there is insufficient research on other languages, for example, Scandinavian languages. Therefore, this research will be focusing on Danish as a second language, inspired by two studies. The first is the Norwegian study that used Gardner's motivation theory for foreigners learning Norwegian (Svanes, 1987). The second is Taiwanese study that used three different approaches to investigate student motivation to learn English in Taipei City, Taiwan (Lai, 2013). This paper thus aims to discover expatriates' motivation for studying Danish from three different theories perspectives: Gardner's motivation theory, Dörnyei's L2 Motivational Self System and Deci & Ryan's self-determination theory. Additionally, the contrast between the theories of expatriates' motivation to learn Danish will also be discussed.

2. Literature review

The literature review will be a discussion of relevant theories, and concepts about second language motivation.

Gardner's Motivation Theory

Gardner and Lambert proposed that an individual's motivation to learn an L2 is maintained by attitudes toward the L2 community, orientations, or the purposes for learning that language (Gardner & Lambert, 1972). Since then, for decades, Gardner's motivation theory with its embodiment model (socio-educational model) has been dominant in the L2 motivation field. According to Gardner, motivation includes three elements: **effort** (the time and energy to learn the language), **desire** (the want and the will to accomplish the goal), and **positive affect** (liking and engaging in language-learning tasks) (Gardner, 2001). In addition, Gardner refers to the orientations' role as a "goal," which aims to increase motivation and achieve the goal (Gardner, 1985).

He and his associates presented, in particular, two types of motivation —integrative and instrumental —that have been substantially explored and discussed in second language acquisition research. For example, Gardner refers to the attitude that individual has towards the L2 community and the desire to adopt some characteristics of their cultural/linguistic group to get close and become a member of that community as integrative motivation (Gardner, 1985). When Dörnyei argues about confusion and the interchanging of integrative motivation in the socio-educational model (Dörnyei, 1994), Gardner clarifies two motivation levels. The first level is the individual's openness towards other cultural groups. However, on the second level, it aims for “complete identification with the community (and possibly even withdrawal from one's original group)”, which may seem excessive. (Gardner, 2001, p. 5). He also points out that the term has “slightly different meanings to many different individuals.” (Gardner, 2001, p. 1)

As a counterpart to integrative motivation, instrumental motivation, or instrumentality, is defined as another variable that affects an L2 learning language achievement for pragmatic reasons, such as getting a better job or a higher salary. Motivation mediates instrumentality and integrativeness; according to Gardner, the three elements, attitudes, integrativeness and instrumentality, are positively interrelated. Therefore, learners who perceive L2 positively while learning, have high integrativeness and instrumentality levels; there is no expectation for them to exist as two independent entities (Gardner, 2005). Dozens of studies have been conducted to discover and compare L2 learners' motivation using Gardner's theory and other theories.

Hsuan-Yau Tony Lai has conducted a study on students from science and technology at a university in New Taipei City (Lai, 2013). The study shows that most participants studied English for instrumental, intrinsic motivation, integrative orientations, travel and the ideal L2 self, but neither because of external pressure nor the ought-to L2 self. He also elaborates that

Taiwanese English learners have been under pressure to have a bicultural identity due to globalization to connect with both the local and the international community. However, since the target language in the study was English, which is an international language, the informants were motivated within different perimeter.

Bjorg Svanes has conducted study in Norway at Bergen university on international students learning Norwegian (Svanes, 1987). The results reported that students from Asia scored highest on instrumental motivation variables. On the other hand, students from the middle east and Africa scored higher on integrative motivation variables. In contrast, students from Western countries scored the highest on integrative motivation variables. Even though Gardner's motivational theory with the socio-educational model has been an exploring and leading model for decades and has been used to test many hypotheses in the field, scholars have criticized the integrativeness notion of the model. (see, for example Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2011; Dörnyei, Csizér, & Németh, 2006; Kachru & Nelson, 2006; Yashima, 2000, 2009).

L2 Self-Motivation System

As mentioned, Gardner's theory has caused confusion and debate about the notion of integrativeness in the L2 motivation. The dissatisfaction with Gardner's notion of integrativeness, led Dörnyei to propose the L2 Motivational Self System to understand L2 motivation (Dörnyei, 2005). Dörnyei and Ushioda coordinate the L2 motivational self-system into different perspectives to view integrative and instrumental motivation as three components:

- 1) Ideal L2 Self represents any characteristic a person would like to own (Dörnyei and Csizér, 2006, p.16). For example, the ideal self regarding the mastery of the second language is a person who is proficient in the second language, in other words, using Gardner's term of having integrative disposition. Moreover, this dimension is here connected to internalized

instrumental motivation. Ideal L2 self seems like a powerful driving force of the desire to diminish the bridge between the actual self to ideal self (Husniyah, 2018).

- 2) Ought-to L2 Self concerns more extrinsic instrumental motivation in this framework. It goes along with Higgins's ought-to self to meet expectations such as duties and obligations and steer clear of adverse outcomes.
- 3) L2 Learning Experience concerns executive motives for the instant learning experiences and milieu (e.g., the influence of curriculum, teacher, peer group, and successful past experiences).

From these three components, we see Dörnyei's L2 Self System is based on one's ability to visualize oneself speaking an L2. Therefore, he emphasizes the L2 learner's powerful imagined self instead of integration into any specific language or cultural group. As a result, L2 learners become closer to his/her ideal L2 self and ought-to L2 self during the process of L2 learning. Moreover, he believes there is a link between integrative and internalized orientation, such as pursuing personal goals and the ideal L2 self, also between the external instrumental motives, such as avoiding punishment or consequences, and the ought-to L2 self, whereas the learning process, environment, and experiences links with L2 learning (Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2009).

Self-Determination Theory.

Although the theory is generally used to describe human motivation in two orientations, i.e., intrinsic, and extrinsic motivation, Ryan and Deci claim they are firmly connected with second language motivation in several ways and are essential for educators (Ryan & Deci 2000). According to Ryan and Deci (1985, 2000), human motivation is categorizable into various types. The first type is amotivation, which is neither caused by internal factors nor external factors, refers to the absence of any desire to act. Ryan & Deci clarify that

amotivation is related to the absence of competence in the individual when practicing an activity. The second type is intrinsic motivation; Ryan and Deci define it as doing an activity for enjoyment and pleasure rather than outside forces or exterior outcomes. The third one is extrinsic motivation; contrary to intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation refers to consequences and adverse outcomes, not doing for the instrumental value itself (Ryan & Deci 1985,200). In addition to that, extrinsic motivation is grouped into four various secondary categories:

- ❖ Integrated regulation (integration).
- ❖ Identified regulation (identification).
- ❖ Introjection, introjected regulation.
- ❖ External regulation.

The degrees of autonomy and self-determination are reflected and differ by these four subcategories through the internalization and integration process.

Ryan and Deci (2000) demonstrate a process of intrinsic/extrinsic motivation change. They believe that human motivation can “move back and forth” between orientations. Therefore, human motivation is not necessarily developed through each stage as a sequence. For instance, a person may start an activity due to external factors such as a reward; nevertheless, while proceeding with the activity/ exercise, the person may find themselves doing well in the activity and could thus increase intrinsic motivation. Moreover, Noels (2001) argues that many orientations or purposes could simultaneously motivate a person to learn an L2, even though some are more important than others, which Lai’s study (2013) has shown.

Second language motivation has been discussed from Gardner’s motivational theory to Dörnyei’s L2 Motivational Self System to Self-Determination Theory in this section. In the following, the methodology of the study will be laid out.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research questions.

The motivation behind acquiring Danish as a second language has not been sufficiently investigated; exploring various dimensions/characteristics was necessary to understand expatriates' motives. Therefore, two questions guided this study to achieve the aim:

1. What are the motives that drive expatriates to learn Danish?
2. Which theory describes/picture their driven motivation in comparison to one another?

Two case studies were selected as the most suitable methodological approach to investigate the research questions because they allowed for two ways to analyze and discuss data. Lai's study (2013) used questions related to three theories in the questionnaire, whereas Svanes' study (1987) applied comparison between different groups. Both methods helped reach answers to the research questions.

3.2 Data collection.

3.2.1 Participants

The study involved online expatriates' communities from various countries and different cultures all living in Denmark. Based on the responses to the first section questions, 52% were from Europe, 23% were from USA, Caribbeans, and New Zealand, 20% were from the South and Southeast Asia, and 5% were from the West and south Africa (see also Table 1). The participants age range between 18-70: 1) 30% between 18-30, 2) 36% between 31-40, 3) 23% between 41-50, 4) 5% between 51-60, and 5) 5% between 61-70. Regarding gender,

66.1% were female, 16 % were males, and 6,8% were “non-binary” (I here use the term “non-binary” for those participants that preferred not to state their gender).

When the participants were asked to evaluate their Danish language proficiency, 40 % answered they were good, and 1,75% answered very well, whereas 31,58% responded bad, and 26,32% responded very bad. The responses to whether they had taken Danish classes were 57% positive (yes) and 42% negative (no), similar to whether they were currently taking Danish classes with 55,9% positive (yes) and 44.1% negative (no).

3.2.2 Survey

For the sake of time and data, a survey questionnaire was generated within onlineundersøgelse, a web-based survey application. In order to obtain comparable data, the questionnaire was based on a questionnaire developed by Chain (2010), and elicited participants’ perceptions and opinions regarding Danish acquisition. The questionnaire was in English and consisted of three sections with Likert-type items. The first section (six questions) solicited respondents’ profile information. Section two contained 32 questions regarding motivational orientations, which were six different orientations as follows:

1. Integrative motivation (7-13)
2. Instrumental motivation (14-16)
3. Intrinsic motivation (17-24)
4. Extrinsic motivation (25-29)
5. Ideal L2 self (30-35)
6. Ought-to L2 self (36-39)

Finally, section three asked the participants for additional comments (see appendix).

Respondents had to assess the items on a scale from 1 to 4 (1=strongly agree; 2= agree; 3= disagree; 4=strongly disagree). A descriptive analysis and an analysis of variances of the

questionnaire data were conducted, which entailed obtaining frequencies of selected-response items and the differences in statistics.

3.3 Limitations

There are some limitations to the study. First, the data might not represent the majority of expatriates in Denmark because they were collected from online expatriates. However, the results still shed some light on how foreigners' motivations have been seen and thought about studying Danish. Second, even though the questionnaire covered six orientations in many aspects of Danish learning motivation, some participants still found that their motives for learning Danish were not mentioned. Therefore, the open-ended question served that purpose, but only 14 comments were received; nevertheless, they still could give an idea about participants' orientations. Danish learners' motivations did differ, and many of them did have many motives to study Danish, as discussed in the literature review that learners may have different motives for learning an L2 (Noels, 2001).

3.4. Measurement error

A four Likert scale was applied, however, two errors occurred while conducting the survey, which may have led to different results:

1. The scale measurement: most common scales go with 1 as strongly disagree, 2 disagree, 3 agree, 4 strongly agree, whereas this questionnaire scale goes in the opposite direction with (1 strongly agree, 2 agree, 3 disagree, and 4 strongly disagree)
2. The questionnaire was simple (see appendix), so it seemed unnecessary to include a midpoint, and an I do not know option, therefore, and it was debatable whether to include or exclude. Nevertheless, it would have been an ultimate advantage if these two options were included.

Although the results would probably have been different without these two errors, they would still not have been substantial. Therefore, replication with a modified scale would be reasonable and highly desired.

4. Results

This study aims to explore expatriates' motivation in Denmark for studying Danish, and compare their motivations in terms of theories mentioned previously. The results were introduced in an inverted pyramid structure, divided into two parts (Figure 1) through two facets:

1. General analysis represented all participants without considering any demographic, i.e., culture, language, or age.
2. Detailed analysis was represented based on the participants' respective countries' geographical location and their common similarities, and then gender and age were considered.

The analyses concluded some marginal differences among the respondents and considerable similarities.

Figure 1.

4.1. General analysis

The results showed differences among the motives that drive the participants to learn Danish. Figure 2 displays the motive that primarily drives the 56 participants: integrative motivation with 89,8% combined (40,4% strongly agreed, and 49,4% agreed). It also exhibits 17% strongly agreed, and 44% agreed on ideal L2 self questions, with 61% combined. Similarly, to ideal L2 self, the respondents with 59 % agree on the intrinsic motivation (13% strongly agree, 46% agree). As Figure 2 shows the highest scores on the extrinsic motivation; contrary to the previous ones, participants' responses are extensively negative. Based on the findings that Figure 2 demonstrates, it may be concluded that this factor demotivates them as 33% disagreed and 63% strongly disagreed, with 96% combined. Using inductive techniques identifies two significant differences in motivation: integrative and extrinsic, besides intrinsic, and ideal L2 self that also play a role in the acquisition of Danish.

4.2. Detailed analysis

This section divided the respondents into four groups according to geographical location, age, and gender, as previously mentioned.

Geographically, they were divided into South and Southeast Asia with 11 members in the group, West, and South Africa with three members, USA, Caribbeans, and New Zealand with 13 members, and Europe with 29 members. The comparison between the groups was not possible due to limited numbers, so the motives and theories were compared inside each group instead.

4.2.1. South and Southeast Asia

The first group was the South and Southeast Asian group, with three females, seven males, and one "non-binary". The participants scored on integrative motivation significantly higher than the other motivations with 79% (19% strongly agree, 60% agree), in comparison, 39% (12% strongly agree, 27 agree) instrumentally. These results contradict the Norwegian

study (Svanes, 1987) and Taiwanese study (Lai, 2013) mentioned earlier, where participants were more instrumentally motivated. In addition to integrative motivation, the participants in this study were in some way intrinsically motivated with 57% (15% strongly agreed and 42% agreed) and in terms of ideal L2 self with 56% (13% strongly agreed 43% agreed). The primary motive for this group was integrative motivation based on the responses, besides intrinsic and Ideal L2 self. However, they responded negatively on extrinsic motivation with 95% (41% strongly disagree and 54% disagree) which could be considered an amotivation. (figure 3).

Distributions of subjects according to sex			
	Men	women	total
South and Southeast Asia	7	3	10
USA, Caribbean, and New Zealand	3	9	12
West and South Africa	1	2	3
Europe	3	24	27
1 Taiwanese, 1 American and 2 Europeans have not reported their sex	4		56

Table 1

4.2.2. West and South Africa

The second group consisted of West and South Africa. The number of respondents who participated in the survey was only three, and therefore, it was impossible to make conclusions as a sample. However, it is important to note that the two participants from South Africa showed they were highly motivated integrally but not as much instrumentally, which corresponded to other motives based on the statistics. This may be considered interesting

because one was a female who was a 70-year-old female, and the other was a 39-year-old male. Despite the age and the gender, no significant differences were found. The participant from Nigeria was only and equally integrally and instrumentally motivated. The three participants responded negatively to extrinsic motivation (Table 2).

Africa	age	sex	integrative	instrumental	intrinsic	extrinsic	ideal L2 self	ought to L2 self
Nigeria	25	Female	2,1	2	2,6	4	2,5	2,8
South Africa/UK	70	female	1,3	2	2,1	3,4	2,3	1,8
South Africa	39	Male	1,9	2,3	2,4	3	2,2	2,3

Table 2 (based on the statistic)

4.2.3. USA, Caribbean, and New Zealand

The third group included the USA, Caribbean, and New Zealand, with two males, one “non-binary”, and nine females. Figure 4 displays the group members scoring higher on the integrative motivation than the other motivations with 87% (33% strongly agree, 54% agree) as the primary motive. In comparison, 30% (14% strongly agree, 16% agree) instrumentally. They are also intrinsically motivated as it also exhibits 76,3 % positive (23 % strongly agreed, and 43 % agreed) on intrinsic motivation. In terms of ideal L2 self, as figure 4 demonstrates, 62% answered positively (21% strongly agree, and 41% agree).

The primary motive for this group is integrative motivation based on the responses, besides intrinsic and Ideal L2 self. However, similarly to the other groups, they responded highly negatively on extrinsic motivation with 96% (37%strongly disagree and 59% disagree).

4.2.4. Europe

The last group included Europe with three males, two “non-binaries” and 24 females. The responses on integrative and instrumental motivation were that 81% (22% strongly

agreed, 59% agreed) integrally motivated, whereas instrumentally, 42% were motivated (17% strongly agreed and 25% agreed). On the responses of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, 58% answered positively on intrinsic motivation (9% strongly agreed, 49 agreed). In comparison, 96 % responded negatively to extrinsic motivation (27% disagreed, 69% strongly disagreed). When asked about the ideal L2 self, 62 % responded positively (17% strongly agreed and 45% agreed). On the contrary, to ought- to L2 self that was about avoiding negative outcome, the responses were 82% negative (41% strongly disagreed, and 41% disagreed). The primary motivation that drives Europeans, based on the responses, was the integrative motivation, besides ideal L2 self, and intrinsic motivation. The results showed that Europeans are highly integrally motivated, which supports the Norwegian study (Svanes, 1987), but they were not motivated extrinsically as in the previous groups, thus it could consider it an amotivation as 96% answered negatively (Figure 5).

Figure 2 (general analysis)

Figure 3 (South and southeast Asia)

Figure 4 (USA, Caribbeans, New Zealand)

Figure 5 (Europe)

Figure 6 (age differences based on the statistic)

Figure 7 (sexes' differences based on the statistic)

4.2.5. Age

The ages of the participants ranged from 18 to 70 (see: participants in figure 6) divided into five groups. Based on the statistic, all participants were integrally and intrinsically motivated. In ideal L2 self, and instrumental motivated, they were also motivated, except two group (51-60 and 61-70). It is essential to note that three participants from the 61-70 group scored the lowest (1,4) on integrative motivation, which means they were highly integrally

motivated. All participants scored very high (negatively) when it came to extrinsic questions and relatively in regard to ought-to L2 self which again showed they were demotivated which could be considered as an amotivation. In terms of age, the primary motivation that drove the participants was the integrative motivation, besides ideal L2 self, and intrinsic motivation (Figure 6).

4.2.6. Sex differences

As the statistics showed, there were some differences between the sexes' motives. Men, women, and "non-binary" showed different motives. For example, women showed different motives for learning Danish: integrative, instrumental, intrinsic, and ideal L2 self, whereas men showed motivation integrative, intrinsic, and ideal L2 self, while "non-binaries" appeared to be only integrally and intrinsically motivated. The statistics exhibited that participants answered highly negatively to extrinsic motivation between the groups, which could be considered again as an amotivation, whereas they answered highly positively on integrative motivation. According to previous findings, the integrative motivation could be considered as a primary motivation in Danish learners, in addition to ideal L2 self and intrinsic motivation. (Figure 7).

4.2.7. Comment section

In the questionnaire, the last question was left for personal opinions; 16 respondents left comments as follows:

1. I want to be able to help my daughter with school she is 5yrs old.
2. It is very hard and language, schools don't know how to do it properly.
3. I learn Danish to learn about my own culture.
4. Provide more tools, and free app can help to make the learning process easier and funny.
5. I study Danish because I live in Denmark.

6. There is an expectation to learn Danish, but Danes prefer speaking English with you. That's absurd.
7. Not technically a foreigner, but I have never lived in Denmark, but I have a Danish mother and Middle Eastern Father whose common language is English.
8. As an older learner, I think some of the questions were irrelevant; what about a not applicable option. Good luck
9. Try adding questions about those individuals wanting to learn Danish for personal, work, residency, etc. who find it difficult to master. There are many people out there who struggle to learn it. Get the pronunciation and annunciation correct so we can be UNDERSTOOD. Danes are not very forgiving in wanting or trying to understand our valiant attempts. Me included.
10. I found a job because I tried to speak in Danish, and I think it would be good also to have a question that cross-checks with people who have found a job because they learned Danish or studied or something. Good luck!.
11. Too old to learn Danish.
12. In my general social environment, everybody speaks English with ease, and my (large, corporate) employer has English as it is a corporate language.
13. I learn Danish because for me, language is an important part of the cultural understanding and because my child also attends a Danish school and I find it important to be able to help her and understand her world.
14. I learn Danish because of the study of my children.

The responses varied between different motives that drove the participants, and even though there was constructive criticism (8 - 10) for the questionnaire. There was also criticism of the learning process and suggestions for improvement (2,4). What was very noticeable was that three (1,13,14) feedbacks were only for the sake of their children and one (10) for a job, which indicates that Danish was just a tool to move forward in the society. There was also a comment related to ought-to-be self (5) if living somewhere, you are supposed to speak the language. One participant expressed confusion (6) with a comment in terms of extrinsic motivation that related to natives' perception of the expatriates. For example, the natives expected ex-pats to speak the language while speaking English to them. However, no conclusion could be made due to the limited number and various subjects of comments.

5. Discussion

The general analysis of the questionnaire data provides two significant differences among participants' motives. First, they are highly integrally motivated, as demonstrated in figure 2 in the previous section. Thusly, integrative motivation is not related to the participants' backgrounds, and as Clément & Kruidenier (1983) explain, the type of motivation differs from one language to another. Second, they have shown significant disagreement with the extrinsic motive. It can even be concluded that this factor demotivates them/ amotivation. In addition to integrative motivation, participants also show other motives that play a role in their motivation, as mentioned earlier in the literature review (Noels, 2001), which are ideal L2 self notion and intrinsic motivation, which indicates that many enjoy learning Danish and imagine themselves speaking Danish fluently.

Ideal L2 self is considered a different dimension of integral and internalized instrumental elements; therefore, the responses were 61 % positive because of the integrative part, not the instrumental one. When the instrumental part was examined separately, it showed a low percentage of participants who were motivated by it. When it comes extrinsic factors which is also associated with ought-to L2 self, the responses were overwhelmingly negative with 96% on extrinsic questions and 75% on ought to L2 self which means the integral and extrinsic are significant contradictory factors within the participants of this study, with a positive factor and a negative one.

The detailed analysis supports both significant records on integrative and extrinsic motivation. When looking at each group in isolation, and compare them to each other, the numbers show more similarity than difference with the groups. However, what is remarkable is that these groups belong to entirely different countries and cultures and with limited groups members, yet they did not score significantly different in terms of the motives that drive them.

Contrarily to Europeans and USA, the Caribbean, and New Zealand, who were expected to score the highest on the integrative motivational questions as they have much in common with Danish culture, the South and Southeast Asians were not expected to score high on integrative questions; however, they did. The reasonable question, as Svanes asked (1987), "how can Asians be interested in a culture that they know very little about? Interest is dependent on some degree of 'preunderstanding' ('Vorverstandnis' Gadamer 1960)" (Svanes, 1987, p. 356). He then clarifies that with Clement and Kruidenier's results (1983), as they explain that motivation can differ in the same group towards different languages. The three West and South African participants also scored higher on integrative and instrumental questions due to their exposure to western culture through colonization (Svanes, 1987, p. 345). (table2)

It must also be noted again that intrinsic motivation in both general and detailed analyses play a role in participants' motivation to learn Danish (figures 2 - 5). On the other hand, instrumental motivation does not play a leading role in this research as it was found in Norway's study for participants from developing countries (Svanes, 1987), and likewise in the Taiwanese study (Lai, 2013). As for sex and age analyses, they do support the same findings that already has been discussed. The majority of the participants in the study learned/have been learning Danish primarily for integrative reasons and pleasure in using Danish, which is seen in their responses to the questionnaire. For example, in terms of integrativeness, when they were asked if they wanted to know more about Danish culture and art, 49% strongly agreed, and 44% agreed, and in terms of intrinsic motivation, when asked if they enjoy speaking Danish, 15% strongly agreed, and 54% agreed (see appendix). So, the fundamental motives that drive the participants in this study are integrative and intrinsic.

6. conclusion

This study aimed to examine learners' orientations for studying Danish through different theories, emphasizing a comparison between them. The findings showed two significant differences among the students' Danish learning motivation. The first was the integrative, which motivated most participants, even though, they were ethnically and culturally diverse, which could also be considered significant. The second one was extrinsic, which responses were extensively negative and can be considered amotivation according to Deci & Ryan (1985). Most participants studied Danish primary for integrative motivation, and besides intrinsic motivation, and the ideal L2 self, not because of external pressure, the ought-to L2 self, or instrumentality.

It is important to note that participants in the Norwegian study were solely university students, as Svanes mentioned. They were probably going back to their home country when they were done with education. It is also important to note that massive, advanced technology occurred since the study was conducted in 1987. Therefore, anytime, anywhere, anyone could learn about any culture in no time, a counterpoint to Svan's idea that Asians have very little knowledge about the Western world. It is also important to note that this study's participants are highly likely to be living in Denmark for some time or plan to settle down. Therefore, language and having a social network within the local community is a long-term strategy for living in any country and culture. As a result, this likely explains why they were highly integrally motivated. Danish as a second language/ foreign language is a field with many opportunities, and would help both researchers and DSL teachers develop new teaching methods to adapt to the learners' motivations.

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